

DESIGN EMOTION BRAND IMAGES ENHANCE SOCIAL VALUE, INSPIRE CHANGE AND INTENSIFY SOCIAL TRANSFORMATION

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ABSTRACT

Brand images spanning a myriad of business applications in advertising, branding and marketing activities have surpassed functional, commercial and financial considerations. Brand image-makers and marketers foray into broader discussions to demonstrate brands' inherent value and position as an emotional element of personal consumption and social interactions. This study seeks to understand the connection between the multitudes of conjured and perceived brand images and their unique capabilities to engage with specific consumers. Gathering survey data from the Malaysian urban consumer segment, this study aims to gain insight into emerging marketing literature, which attests to the emotional and social roles of brand image. Results reveal consumers' increased awareness and perception of today's successfully marketed brands, and a positive image emerges when brands visibly demonstrate target consumer engagement with emotional benefits, ideas that inspire social change and intensify social transformation. Social experiences with brands are a leading factor in enhancing marketing management strategies today, as businesses have greater opportunities to address, contribute to, and facilitate relevant social conversations through salient brand images.

KEYWORDS: *Brand Image, Brand Identity, Emotional Benefits, Social Value, Consumer Experience*

INTRODUCTION

Brand Image vs. Brand Identity: Some Term Definitions

Brands as a marketing concept and a social phenomenon have always been hard to characterise or describe utilising key definitions, making its study both a stimulating and reflective discourse in the development of marketing management perspectives. Dr Philip Kotler, distinguished marketing professor, sets the stage for this discussion by defining brand image as 'a set of beliefs that consumers hold about a particular brand' (2005, p. 282). Products manufactured, sold, and distributed by a particular company under a particular name as such carry a distinct image, and consumers would ascribe, interpret, or construct their own set of cognitive or affective responses that bears meaning to themselves or others, based on experiences, emotional benefits, social symbolisms and other dimensions (Aaker, 1991, 1992, 1996; Keller, 1993).

The American Marketing Association (2008) defines 'brand' more perfunctorily, as 'a name, term, sign, symbol, design, or a combination of features that identifies the goods or services of one seller or group of sellers and differentiates them from those of other sellers'. A brand projects the image of a particular organisation, product or service that consumers associate with, and marketing the brand image means making a careful selection of marketing mix criteria, considering the economic, cultural and social conditions which influence consumers' buying behaviours (Lake, 2009).

Global brand strategy consultant Professor David Aaker define brand identity as 'a unique set of brand associations that the brand strategist aspires to create or maintain' (Aaker, 1996, p.68). By extension, brands, whether they are the outcome of consumers' impressions and perceptions, but in having intrinsic equity value as economic entities, must be managed systematically (Keller, 1993). Omnipresent brands find their way to retailers and consumers in every aspect as a result of

functional and symbolic image congruity or alignment in people's impression, awareness, product involvement or utility, lifestyles, needs, and aspirations (Jing Hu et al, 2012). Every interaction with a brand counts, and advertising can undeniably affect society's perception of brand images; from memorable designs, logos, and slogans that compete for attention; billboards, magazines, websites, and a host of tangibles and intangibles (Jing Hu et al., 2012, p.2).

Branding processes and activities go along with marketing ideas to consumers to increase recognition and differentiation from competitors (McEnally & de Chernatony, 1999, p.17), yet volatile markets increase brands' susceptibility to competitive marketing in global environments, unless companies have long term positioning strategies mapped out (Ries & Trout, 1981, cited in McEnally & de Chernatony, 1999, p.13). It thus behoves that success in brand-building campaigns and brand loyalty relationships go hand-in-hand with understanding consumers (Light, 1994). Malik et al. (2012) argue for businesses to invest time to survey, research, define, and reinforce the brand in creating positive consumer awareness, top-of-mind recall and salience, leading to preference, purchase intention, and loyalty. Other studies view the relative construct of brand images: Kim et al. (2008), for instance, describe unique service as that which carries a brand image in consumers' minds, and that is identified and positioned to stand out from competitors.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

Brands have evolved from their traditional missions in pursuit of profit and the promotion of consumerism, to providing a range of personalised promises and added value to engender loyalty. The aim of this research is to examine links between consumer attitudes and perceptions of brand images' emotional design construct and the impact that results from their evolving roles in inspiring change and intensifying social transformation.

Driven by development in brand research, the current study attempts to answer several key questions, namely:

- What underlying relationships are conveyed by brand images today?
- How do consumer interaction and experiences with these images correlate to their emotional and social needs fulfilment?
- How could brand images communicate emotional benefits, which reflect consumers' social values and aspirations for change?

The objectives of this study are to review the role of brands through their economic and social contexts in order to understand brands' contributions in terms of psychological and emotional benefits, and social value. This study attempts to analyse the level of brand image awareness among a sampling of survey respondents from the urban demographical segment in Malaysia, and to determine the connection of brand image to purchasing behaviour.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The researcher begins studying a selection of literature, to develop perspectives to the question often raised, 'Why the buzz about brands?'. This is premised on the general public assumption that brands are mere corporate identity emblems and logos. Misconceptions and distorted ideas about brands may impact judgment and produce negative sentiments towards organisations (Pallotta, 2011). Brands in fact communicate more than marketplace information through ubiquitous logos. Kotler and Keller (2009) argue that brands affect businesses besides being associated with products: in the acceleration globalised environment, their roles and agents of customer loyalty permeate markets in different economic, cultural, and social conditions. The benefit of strong brand images not only sustains market equity for the business in the long run, but shapes economic opportunities through their indirect role in maintaining economic and social progress in terms of enhanced living standards, educational and job opportunities, health, safety, transportation, and much more. This paper argues for a broader impact of the influence of brand images through four key roles: namely, that it rationalises consumer interaction; facilitates economic development, creates social value; promotes innovation and cooperation and removes cross-cultural barriers, thus inspiring social transformation. The following sections further this discussion with case study examples of the roles of brand image constructs.

Brand Image in Consumer Interaction

Social entrepreneur and *Harvard Business Review* blogger Dan Pallotta (2011) believes that a brand 'is peoples' gut feeling about the organisation', and that in and within every level of customer interaction lays the signifier of their concern or interest in that brand, this view accords with the thought-provoking commentaries on brand positioning strategies undertaken by Ries and Trout in the 1980s (Malik et al., 2012, p.13070).

Brand identities rationalise consumer rights advocacy efforts via tangible brand promises (Trout, 2008), that consumers may expect to enjoy assurance of quality, integrity, and reliability in the provision of goods or services, such as displaying precise information, exceptional customer service and warranties, compliance with environmental, health, safety and labour regulations and other consumer protection benchmarks (Hilton, 2003). Aside from selling benefits, respectable brands in the marketplace assure consumers of quality, and the use of brand design elements help companies meet its consumers confidently. Brand images reflect enjoyment of particular aspects of consumption and social status, besides communicating an individual's aspirational values and enriching consumers' shared connections (Saade, 2010). Consumer behaviour and marketing research study the relationships between brand personalities, self-identity, and social interests, and how these concepts influence and correlate with target audience's expectations, self-expression and experiences (Aaker, 1996; Malik et al, 2012; McEnally & de Chernatony, 1999, p.16). Self-confidence, status, and aspiration are talking points via

associative brands, designed to affect one's image and express inner attributes. Brands, which represent preferences in food, clothing, arts, music, and hobbies, enhance followers' ability to acquaint themselves with like-minded people. Vitality, for businesses to develop, manage, and project the brand personality that fits target audiences, brand image advertising must have relevance, salience and significance to the latter's characteristics, backgrounds, and inclinations. With globalisation of markets driving economic growth, strategic brand awareness must take into account multicultural contexts in order to be realised (Palumbo and Herbig, 2000). Additionally, the pervasiveness of brands across cultural milieus is a result of being communicated with greater freedom in traditional, international and niche media (Kotler et al., 2005, p.773). The ease by which brands engage consumers makes them effective as a cultural tool: as such, marketers must improve awareness and insights on their related appeals, as the dialogue between what brands represent and the way this influences consumers becomes a close integration of knowledge and practice (Kotler & Keller, 2009).

Brand Image in Economic Development

Miriam Greenberg in her book *Branding New York* reflects on how the 'image crisis', which struck New York City in the 1970s, produced widespread urban chaos, as a series of civic unrests and worker strikes harmed fiscal ratings, real estate values, tourist perceptions and threatened economic opportunities, while urban poverty and interracial conflicts worsened the social fabric of the community, leading to drug addiction and widespread crime (Chan, 2008). The city leadership, mired in large-scale crises, viewed glitzy promotional efforts as 'ancillary, if not irrelevant to their overall strategy of economic development ...' (Greenberg, 2008).

Efforts to refashion New York's image were undertaken in the late 1970's with a slew of public-private tie-ups. Campaigns helped boost local economic growth, and in spite of spasmodic social protests in the form of severely defaced subways, these helped turn around the tarnished label of New York from 'Fear City' to 'The Big Apple' (Chan, 2008). The New York State Department of Commerce launched the 'I Love New York' campaign in 1976, emblematically captured by native New York artist Milton Glaser through the 'I ♥ New York' logo. Image-making mechanisms founded on emotional appeals prompted the restructuring of local political and economic relationships, and with the help of marketers, artists and designers, musical directors and other cultural industry professionals reformed attitudes, shifted real estate values and investor confidence (Greenberg, 2008). The rebranding shifted New York's position into a spanking new commercial and financial hub without the use of large-scale official marketing budgets.

From a triumph of crisis response, not coincidentally, nearly 140 million tourists today flock to the Empire State annually; while, in the ingenious process of commercialising its image, almost 3,000 trademark objections have arisen as the 'I ♥ New York' logo design is openly used, cloned and parodied (Dorsch, 2005). Magazines portray New York City as 'a hip place to live,

work, and shop for young, social climbing urbanites' (Greenberg, 2008), and this image has obviously been lovingly and painstakingly fostered. The strong branding has sustained visitor rates up to the present decade.

Brand Image in Promoting Innovation

Brands attract users beyond traditional consumption. Besides generating commercial and social value in the marketplace, their newly acquired role in modern consumer society today is to contribute to community well-being. The demand for brand images today is to symbolically construct and generate meaning that align with target consumers' own identities (Venkatesh & Meamber, 2006, p.26), paving the way for a competitive playing field, which indirectly promotes innovation. This enhances opportunities for brands, as they must risk innovating and continually develop new products, thus promoting differentiations from one another. As adaptation becomes a key value of nimble brands, companies that own distinctive brand images must strive to provide a range of choices and meet consumer preferences based on an individual's criteria, whether the choice is personal, behavioural or socially motivated. Product development becomes a game of one-upmanship among brand owners, hence, besides serving and satisfying target markets, brands must keep pace and strive to represent an image of excellence, as companies create a virtuous upward spiral of continuous innovation (Lindemann, 2004).

Social responsibility initiatives has arisen in the past two decades to form the basis of brand conversations among consumers, corporations, governments, global agencies, and other stakeholders (Keller, 1993). As discerning users migrate to the Internet, they are keen to scour and share information about brands, 'rather than [hear] what marketers want to say' (Mitchell, 1997, cited in McEnally & de Chernatony 1999, p.18). The era of passive message reception is long over: consumers are proving their energetic involvement in brand creation by comparing user experiences and reviews; enquiring, understanding, and confirming information; tracking competitors and seeking insights, before forming attitudes and views toward the brand.

These pose a tremendous challenge for supply-side marketers, as fractured markets require needs-based market segmentation (Piercy, 1997, cited in McEnally & de Chernatony, p.18). Successful brand designs must factor in long-run survival, and this involves employee engagement programmes (e.g. Shell), corporate social responsibility (McDonalds' local community initiatives), and a greater emphasis on environmental stewardship (e.g. Nike using organic cotton and other environmentally preferred footwear materials: *Nike, Inc*, n.d.). By expressing its larger social values and mission, an organisation's brand image provides buy-in factors that shape stakeholder perceptions. As increased global warming threatens Earth with wide-scale devastation, sustainability and other environment-related conversations become topical. Brands could catalyse acts of change in terms of its roles and effort to conserve nature's resources. Canvas grocery bags, reusable

food containers, and energy-saving features provide consumers with ethical choices through environmental-friendly packaging and products.

A 2010 study found that 94% of consumers are concerned about the environmental effects of beverage packaging, with 60% Millennials and Gen-Xers willing to pay more for environmentally friendly products (Shayon, 2011). Brown-bagging instead of plastic bags, discounted coffee purchase for tumbler owners, green-tech mobile phones, delivery trucks that run on hybrid systems, petroleum-free soda cans, recyclable merchandise display rack, and organic fashion ranges demonstrate a willing change for Earth's sake. Other strategic branding partnerships with non-governmental organisations enable brands to improve their social responsibility outreach via media and social campaigns, as brand owners supply funds to sustain on-going projects or reach targeted audiences, including rural educational activities, clean water access, medical research, and coordinating donations for victims of calamities.

Estée Lauder's annual breast cancer awareness campaign produced the ubiquitous symbol of breast health, the Pink Ribbon. More than 85 million Pink Ribbons have been distributed worldwide, with millions of dollars raised towards the Breast Cancer Research Foundation (Lauder, n.d). RED is a brand licensed by The Global Fund, which partners corporation such as Nike, Apple Inc., Starbucks, Converse, Gap, Motorola, Dell and others to increase awareness and funding for HIV/AIDS related programmes. Dove's *Campaign for Real Beauty* aims to alter the Western concept of beauty, giving women an esteem boost beyond looking good while staying true to Dove's mission 'to make more women feel beautiful everyday' by narrowing stereotypical views of beauty. The definitive force of Dove's social branding influence for the core message via various advertising and social media platforms has garnered a multi-million viewership and sparked heated global debates (Dove, n.d.), proving how purposeful campaigns for social change via brand identification result in adding value to customer relationships and making a positive impact on stakeholders.

Brand Image in Creating Social Value

Fundamentally, the greatest brand images in the world seek to be social unifiers. Coca-Cola sought to teach the world to sing; Nike celebrates human endeavour; Nokia connects people; Lux soap gives Asian women self-confidence; Budweiser made heroes out of blue-collar workers (Hilton, 2003).

One of the most important keys to lasting consumer relations lies with the emotional benefits offered by the brand. Today's marketplace is awash with a garbled confusion of choices, and understanding the psychological models behind consumers' socialisation processes is a definite asset in contemporary marketing research and practice (Moschis & Smith, 1985).

One approach would be to study the affective connections customers develop and value in brand interactions, and how this determines or potentiates behavioural change in target consumers or social groups. Among the burgeoning, noteworthy trend in brand studies has been the marketing in niche

products and services that reflect individuals' personalities, as well as the successful advertising and promotion of brand personalities via word-of-mouth. For brands to evoke emotional attachments, consumers' values and beliefs take precedence to produce behavioural response, i.e. purchase intention and action (Jacoby & Chestnut, 1978).

Self-expressions, self-definitions and self-presentations are important considerations, and marketers must add on to their portfolio of skills a capacity to unleash the intrinsic and extrinsic values of brands the very same recognised and esteemed by devotees as authentic symbols of the social groups they actually (or aspire to) belong to (McEnally & de Chernatony, 1999, p.16). People react to, and desire, brands that are congruent with their character, using it to express internal attributes; the slogan of brands are promises spoken to effect behavioural and attitudinal response.

Nike encapsulates the emotional character of triumph in its slogan, *Just Do It*, and the use of star athletes in advertising endorsements (Bedbury, 2002). Through a plethora of associations, the product's image moves through altercasting, and projects what it stands for (winning), thereby boosting its innate brand value (McEnally & de Chernatony, 1999, p.30). Aside from promoting sportsmanship, the brand tag deems courage and enjoyment of endeavouring as worthy attributes. Apple's *Think Different* speaks of a constant willingness to innovate, to get away from one's comfort zone, and aim for self-improvement and creativity. Clearly, both these brands inspire people emotionally, arousing their hope to pursue change, thus providing a positive force to accomplish desired results.

Starbucks' brand image revolves around a great coffee experience; quality coffee beans brewed at the right temperature served in plush store environments, setting the tone for java-fuelled enjoyment (Bedbury, 2002). When Guinness ran the *Guinness Irish Pub* giveaway, contestants went all out in poetry writing and pint pulling, steeping into the Irish community's authentic cultural values via the traditional Irish pub environment (Bedbury, 2002: 98-99). Coca-Cola's *The Real Thing* and BMW's *Ultimate Driving Machine* are examples of brand promises that have grown beyond mere slogans, evolving into living icons for the company and their believers (Trout, 2008).

It is a given that humans are emotional beings who constantly need to express themselves, to feel belongingness, and to go in search of others with similar interests in hope of forming, entering, or enlarging their social circles. As people identify others of similar or different socio-economic groups, they recognise social parallels and differences in terms of speech, behaviour, values, or consumption preferences. People with similar taste in music, movies, fashion, love of travel, etc. may converse in insider 'language' forms. Brands which symbolise certain lifestyles like Abercrombie & Fitch, Harley-Davidson, Armani, and others, construct symbolic insights into specific lifestyle behaviours from likes and dislikes, to what keeps them satisfied. A person's habits and behavioural routines are often crucial descriptors of the individual. Chanel perfume, Tag Heuer timepieces, Fender guitars and Nike sneakers affect image and express inner attributes.

The upshot of the search for social approval would be a motivation towards approaching the ideal image, and the tendency would be an image or self-esteem boost through brands in order to alter people's perceptions about them. Elites, to whom social recognition of respectability and self-worth are deemed essential, often recourse to such devices, without which they may perceive indifference of others towards their accomplishments.

Akin to having a trusted circle, research shows consumers choose brands the way we interact with others who are compatible with our attitudes, personality, outlook and views (Aaker, 1996; McEnally & de Chernatony, 1999, p.13, Kotler, 2005, p.71). Brand images allow people to create desires, a crucial force in individual's aspiration for success, where products and services are outlets or mechanisms for self-reward and pampering. Moreover, brand images are symbolic embodiments denoting certain lifestyles and consumption behaviours or preferences. The brand association behind the symbol, design or label suggests belongingness (McEnally & de Chernatony, 1999). Such a socially empowering concept could range from 'sophistication', 'adventurous', 'middle aged', 'eco-friendly' and all their attendant emotional benefits. Abraham Maslow's contribution to humanistic psychology, the *Hierarchy of Needs* was conceptualised to model the basis of his assumption that were motivated by unsatisfied needs.

A core human value is to belong to something larger than us. This desire to belong to a larger group is so deeply embedded in our primal tribal histories that organisations clamber over each other to fill this essential need in targeted customers (Bedbury, 2002). Maslow's *Hierarchy of Needs* describes the sense of belonging and acceptance as a requisite need that must be met before one ascends towards self-esteem and self-actualisation. The stress on notable personal attainments, such as 'social victory', is a fulfilment of our desire for intimate and affectionate relationships (Kunc, 1992).

Images are powerful group identifiers, the social natures of which imbue our family, peers, and neighbours with the same attitudes, values, interests and aspirations. Where loyalty is gained through habitual, emotionally satisfying experiences in consumers' purchase decision (Jacoby & Chestnut, 1978), brand images' could produce causative factors through strong emotional appeals. Social identification via brands connects us tangibly with peers of similar values, interests and aspirations, consumption patterns, tastes etc., and these help aggregate them into certain communities of mutual yet diverse interests. Brands that are symbols of certain lifestyles include Abercrombie & Fitch, Harley-Davidson, Armani, Louis Vuitton, Quiksilver, Roxy, Billabong, Mini Cooper, Starbucks, etc.

Brands could analyse these social relationships to interpret 'connectedness' using the design emotion model; that is, by complementing the emotional dimension with every point of communication in the consumer interaction chain (Pullman & Gross, 2004). Examples include brand image expression of safety and security (Volvo), freedom (Harley Davidson), adventure and youth culture (Red Bull), etc.

Loyalty helps brands achieve income returns and economic goals by being unique and distinctive, but this should not be at the expense of being cheap (Light, 1994). Revenue growth is a direct result of nurturing strategic customer relationships (Kotler, 2005, p.101), and this rests on the image of service reliability, quality and assurance, brand evangelising through word-of-mouth, or evaluation of user experiences among peers and acquaintances. For brands with strong equity such as high recognition or preference, customers are willing to pay higher prices just to get the product even if this comes at a loss (Reichheld, 1993). Loyalty becomes a habitual act in consumer interaction across espoused personal values, beliefs, social, or cultural norms, symbolising the positive, superior or competitive attributes of the brand image for the consumer that produces product involvement (Hanzaee et al., 2011).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study involved a survey of urban adults, aged between 18-27 years. A simple random sampling method was used, and a total of 120 participants were given a timeframe of 45 days to respond, in the survey conducted online from mid-May to the end of June 2013. Respondents comprised employed professionals, executives, and managers, as well as self-employed individuals and students, providing internet access regardless of their location within Malaysia.

Research Instrument

To evaluate respondent perceptions and awareness about brands and the effects of brand images, a structured online questionnaire was designed and distributed via <https://docs.google.com/>. This method enabled the researcher to analyse and note overall respondents' enjoyment and awareness of brand images, and how they evaluated the effectiveness and capacity of the brands in their consumption. The late adolescent and young adult age segment was chosen due to the greater exposures to media influences for respective segments, enabling them to examine and elicit responses which demonstrate their critical awareness of brands.

A series of relevant brand image-related questions were asked in attempt to analyse, record and interpret data related to the respondents' attitudes, behaviours and perceptions towards brands. From the total 120 returned questionnaires, data was collated and studied to determine the relevance, salience, and the significance of the brand image to their self-expression, personal experiences, views, and social values in consumption. Due consideration was given to ensure cultural relevance of questions to the Malaysian background.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The data produced from the study shows brand preference and attitudes were correlated to consumption decisions that

Do you buy only reputable products with a positive image?

Pie Chart 1

Would you agree that the use of familiar brand images has improved your personal confidence and overall wellbeing?

Pie Chart 4

Do you agree brand image can influence customer loyalty on any particular brand?

Pie Chart 2

Would you agree that brands play a role in the improvement of the economy and living standards in countries?

Pie Chart 5

Would you agree that inspiring brand images and slogans play a role to affect your feelings, beliefs, opinions and decisions?

Pie Chart 3

Would you agree that brand images are a form of motivator that encourage you to achieve your goals?

Pie Chart 6

gave insight on participants' levels of brand awareness, and emotional benefits gained from individual and collective engagement with brands.

Pie Chart 1 shows that 68% buy products perceived as 'reputable' from association with its positive image. Pie Chart 2 reveals that 90 out of 120 people, or 75%, think that brand images may influence consumer brand loyalty.

Pie Chart 3 shows 55% of respondents benefited emotionally from the slogan of brands, agreeing on the role of brand identities in shaping their emotions. Pie Chart 4 shows only 10%, or 12 respondents, did not believe branded products could improve their confidence or wellbeing.

Pie Chart 5 shows 72, or 60%, are aware that brands contribute to the world economy with living standards; 40% of respondents think that brands are not deemed functional or important assets that enhance a country's economic position. Pie Chart 6 shows that 85%, or 102 out of 120 participants, are motivated by specific brand images to attain their desired goals. In this study, the findings found that consumers' brand

awareness has extended beyond quality and price-conscious purchasing. Brand relationships exist in positive and beneficial ways, and are salient to consumers' personal and social perspectives, besides influencing their consumption preferences and improving the value they seek in social interactions with others.

Among the varied factors that created customer loyalty, *Visual Experience* gained 36 votes, followed by *Quality*, which received 30 votes. *Price* and *Advertisement* received an equal vote of 18 each, and *Packaging* scored 12 votes. A little over half the respondents agreed that brand images have helped express or define their personalities or in gaining status or respect; others were not really concerned about the brand image aspect, which infers that pricing, performance and quality were more important drivers.

108 out of 120 respondents agree that possessing branded products boosted their confidence. With current social pressures, individuals wishing to avoid social rejection or humiliation find branded goods and their identifiers useful in reckoning

stature upgrade and social confidence. Quality products appeal to their rational consumption motives, but brands reflect their social status as informed consumers with socially approved good taste. 72 respondents affirmed that brands' play a role in raising living standards of countries in some ways, and brand images are valuable motivators that poise them for further social successes and challenges. Consumption of well-placed brands enable them to plan purchases ahead in order to obtain the product or service desired, while some used brands as a form of enjoyment, for self-reward or pampering purposes.

SUGGESTIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

Research shows that brand personalities contribute to the growth of local economies, giving a social and affective dimension to individuals' consumption experience (Aaker, 1996; McEnally & de Chernatony 1999). This study found a strong correlation between Malaysian consumers' awareness via brand image engagement and their personal and social perspectives. Just *how much* brand images influence consumption preferences or their engagement with others in social conversations is an untapped area of research. It is evident upon close analysis of data from this survey that consumers today demand more than quality in brand experiences. Social experiences can produce brand encounters, and research can improve understanding of the salience of brands' emotional linkages which transcend company attributes, logo design, or trademark recognition (Pallotta, 2011).

The lack of impactful of local studies on consumer perceptions is the single-most important factor to urge on brand marketing research initiatives; hence, future research could affect the cultivation of brands' social value, and therefore the potential of this relationship should be further field-tested. Greater exchange platforms will require greater industry and scholarly knowledge sharing among advertising and media experts and marketing managers, and these could discuss social branding themes such as the role of social connections in building brand loyalty; and brands which spur a constant search for personal achievement or to exceed social expectations. Most retailers understand the need to connect emotionally with consumers; yet, a good many do not know how (or are not trying to) put principle into practice, neglecting the social and emotional valuation in lieu of low price promises, which appeal to customers' sense of reason, but eschews their passions (Berry, 2001). Another notable implication from this study is that brand image reputation, along with consumers' positive brand experiences and aspirational motives are signs of brands' approachability. Future studies could contemplate factors, which boost brand equity and brands' potential to set a price premium over the cost of provision, thus increasing willingness to purchase. Quantitative studies could be replicated in non-urban segments to evaluate whether price, performance, quality and desire for value comes with the proviso of socially-responsible merchants that bear positive brand identities.

CONCLUSION

Society today is daily educated to recognise the importance of brands. Brand management essentially, the process of constructing, developing and sustaining brands has evolved from the bricolage of artifices of past practice; generating designs, images, labels, slogans, etc., and continues erratically today to produce a new vision of organisational identity where ingrained cultural values clash mightily, 'spontaneously and stochastically' (Massi & Harrison, 2008, p.4) with the aesthetics of postmodern values and the pastiche of new media simulated realities and hyper-reality tools (Massi & Harrison, 2008, p.3). Brands draw us into wider discursive implications that are at once social, political, economic, and moral in nature. Our conception of purpose, profit and passions can be promptly analysed from what we spend on social goods (Hilton, 2003). To boost fairer economic goals in the midst of widening inequality, brands must be couched as sustainable symbols, delivering both quantifiable and immeasurable benefits to their target publics, whilst being malleable, transforming and moving to integrate shifts in our emotional and values spectra.

Stakeholders demand new consumer standards to be met in a range of ways: re-examination of corporation ethics and brands' contributions to the economy and living standards; continuous social innovation to improve brand value and competitive positioning through consumer advocacy; assessing and managing global business opportunities to strengthen brand equity and improve perceptions of what unique brands stand for (Aaker, 1991; Hall, 1999; Lindemann, 2004). By summing up a company's best and worst experiences, brand images represent a raft of associated aspects linking attitudes, emotions, and motivational appeals to consumption behaviour, and these are the cumulative outcomes of brand interactions. This will be a fundamental attribute for businesses steering their brands to further heights, as valuable social conversations with staunch consumers inspire the latter to continue being part of the brand-making process.

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